

Advances in AI-Driven Fish Disease Detection: A Comprehensive Review of Image-Based and Machine Learning Approaches (2019–2025)

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Abstract:

Fish disease outbreaks continue to pose a major challenge to global aquaculture by causing mortality, reduced growth performance, and economic losses. Rapid and accurate disease detection is therefore pivotal for health management in fish farming systems. In recent years, artificial intelligence based methods have drawn interest as tools for automating disease detection and enabling non-invasive monitoring in aquaculture. This review examines eight peer-reviewed studies published between 2019 and 2025, with developing research primarily densely between 2021 and 2024, that applied artificial intelligence techniques for fish disease detection. The studies mainly focused on image-based analysis using machine learning and deep learning models like CNN, along with advancing non-invasive and integrated monitoring frameworks. The convolutional neural network based models were most commonly employed for identifying externally visible disease symptoms from fish images, while some studies investigate hybrid systems that combined visual data with additional environmental information. The studied literature confirms a the potential of AI driven methods for automated fish disease screening under controlled experimental conditions. However, several limitations remain evident, including small and species specific datasets, different image quality, limited field validation, and challenges related to model interpretability and application in real under water environment. The findings of this review indicate that AI-based fish disease detection has progressed significantly, further research is needed to improve reliability, consistency, and practical applicability. Future efforts should prioritize standardized data information, field level validation, and user system design to support the adoption of affordable and reliable AI tools for fish health management.

Keywords: *Fish Disease Detection; Artificial Intelligence; Deep Learning; Machine Learning; Image-Based Diagnosis; Non-Invasive Monitoring.*

Introduction:

Fish farming has become one of the rapidly expanding food producing sectors worldwide, contributing to global fish supply, food security, and livelihood, particularly in developing regions (FAO, 2023; Bondad-Reantaso et al., 2005). Fisheries account for meeting the rising demand for meat, animal protein and supporting economic development. Though aquaculture practices has also increased disease infection and outbreaks, which put limitations on productivity and sustainability in fish farming systems (Peterman & Posadas, 2019). Still, the sustainability and productivity of aquaculture systems are continually challenged by infectious and non-infectious fish diseases, which increases

mortality, impaired growth performance, and marked economic losses (Bondad-Reantaso et al., 2005). Disease outbreaks are problematic in intensive farming systems, where early detection and timely intervention are important for effective health management (FAO, 2022). Fish diseases can result in economic losses due to mortality, reduced growth rates, higher diagnosis, treatment costs, and trade restrictions. Stress inducing factors in environmental such as temperature, depletion of dissolved oxygen, imbalance in pH, and accumulation of toxic substances are contributors to disease susceptibility and outbreak in fish farming systems (Overstreet & Curran, 2004; Maldonado-Miranda et al., 2022). Effective disease management

therefore depends on early detection and timely intervention, particularly in intensive and semi-intensive farming environments.

In the era of Computational technology in fisheries AI helped in resource management and enhance sustainable practices (Abedin et al., 2022). Studies have shown that integrating image-based disease detection with IoT-enabled environmental monitoring improved predictive performance by linking water quality parameters such as temperature, dissolved oxygen, and ammonia concentration with disease susceptibility in aquaculture systems (Timmis et al., 2017). Traditional fish disease diagnosis depends on visual observation, parasitological examination, and laboratory-based analyses, which are labor-intensive, time-consuming, and impractical at the farm level (Noga, 2010). Such methods identify disease only after clear clinical symptoms appear, inhibiting the preventive management strategies. , There is rapid growth interest in developing automated, non-invasive disease detection tools that can operate under real-world conditions. In fisheries technology, Advancing artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning are used for improving fish health monitoring. Image-based machine learning techniques have proved itself for detecting visible fish diseases by analyzing surface features such as external injury , discoloration, and abnormal morphological changes (Ahmed et al., 2021; Azhar et al., 2024). Deep learning systems are often treated as black-box classifiers, providing little insight into the features or environmental variables driving disease predictions. This lack of transparency can reduce user trust and prohibit practical adoption, particularly when automated outputs inform management decisions. Recent studies have highlighted the importance of explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) frameworks to improve transparency and support decision-making in biological systems (Gunning et al., 2021). Recently research highlights a deviation toward non-invasive and multi-index fish health assessment frameworks that integrate visual analysis with sensing modalities,

combining environmental and impedance-based measurements, to improve disease monitoring and risk assessment (Zhang et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2023). Transparency is further enhanced through the inclusion of explainable machine vision methods, which is considered important for building user trust and facilitating practical adoption by farmers and aquaculture managers. (Isaac et al., 2024; Islam et al., 2024).

Studies which are existing have been conducted under controlled experimental conditions, with limited evaluation across different species and environmental settings. This indicates the need for a systematic review of recent research to assess methods, identify gaps, and propose future research directions in fish disease detection. Accordingly, the present study examines studies published between 2019 and 2025 on fish disease detection, focusing on image-based methods, machine learning approaches, and systems that integrate environmental data.. By analyzing current advances and identifying challenges, this review aims to provide an overview of the state of the art and to outline directions for future research and practical implementation in aquaculture health management. Given the rapid growth of AI-driven fish disease detection research and the diversity of methodologies employed, a comprehensive and systematic synthesis of recent advances is required (Halevy et al., 2009).

Methodology:

To ensure transparency and reproducibility the review was carried using a systematic methodology guided by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework (Page et al., 2021). A literature search was carried out across multiple electronic databases such as. Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, PubMed, IEEE Xplore, and ResearchGate. The existing research papers were chosen to cover biological sciences, fish research, and computational artificial intelligence literature to identify relevant studies published between 2019 and 2025, a period reflecting the growing application of

deep learning and IoT-assisted systems. The literature search was conducted using combinations of keywords related to fish disease detection. Disease-specific and aquaculture-related terms, including “machine learning,” “AI detection,” “fish lesions,” “aquaculture health monitoring,” and “underwater image analysis,” were also employed to ensure adequate coverage of the relevant domain. Fish disease detection, artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, image-based diagnosis, and IoT-based aquaculture monitoring, using Boolean operators to refine results. Studies were selected primarily on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria, Only studies addressing externally observable fish diseases and reporting image-based, sensor-based, or hybrid AI models refereed relevant were included focusing on research that applied AI-driven methods for fish disease detection using image data, environmental sensor data, or hybrid approaches .The PRISMA-based screening process involved duplicate removal, title and abstract screening, and full-text eligibility assessment, resulting in the inclusion of eight studies for final synthesis. Relevant data concerning fish species, disease types, AI types and more to methods, data sources, dataset traits, performance metrics, and reported limitations were systematically extracted to enable comparison across studies. Every study was qualitatively assessed for potential sources of bias, including dataset size limitations, species specificity, controlled experimental conditions, and reliance on accuracy as a primary evaluation metric, in line with recommended practices for reviewing AI applications in biological systems (Moher et al., 2009). Due to variability in data matrix , AI architectures, and assessment protocols, quantitative meta-analysis was not feasible; therefore, Instead of statistical summarization, the findings were examined through a structured qualitative comparison (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006). Although the review timeframe spanned 2019–2025, no studies meeting the inclusion criteria were identified for 2019 and 2020, reflecting the limited application

of AI-based fish disease detection during the early phase of this period.

Results of the Systematic Review:

The PRISMA-guided screening process resulted in the inclusion of eight peer-reviewed publications published between 2019 and 2025 that examined artificial intelligence based methods for fish disease detection. The literature which was selected primarily addressed diagnosis of image-based disease , machine learning driven classification methods, and hybrid systems incorporating environmental or sensor based information. The literature revealed clear methodological patterns in terms of AI model designs, disease categories addressed, and reported performance outcomes. Deep learning techniques especially convolutional neural networks (CNNs) were most frequently employed for image-based fish disease detection. Convolutional neural network (CNN) based models were employed for the automatic extraction of visual features from fish images, enabling the identification of externally visible disease signs, including lesions, ulcers, discoloration, and abnormal surface patterns. Image based deep learning methods showed acceptable performance for early stage disease screening under controlled experimental conditions when adequate quantities of labelled image data were available (Ahmed et al., 2021; Azhar et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2023). Studies addressed limitations associated with dataset size and variability. In these cases, transfer learning and model fine-tuning were applied to pre-trained deep learning architectures to support fish disease detection, allowing feature extraction from relatively small image datasets (Azhar et al., 2024; Isaac et al., 2024). Such methods indicate a gradual methodological shift toward improving model performance in data-limited aquaculture settings.

In addition to deep learning approaches, some studies employed conventional machine learning techniques, including support vector machines and other feature-based classifiers. These methods relied on manually derived visual

descriptors from fish images and generally yielded moderate classification accuracy. Although computationally less complex and easier to implement, traditional machine learning approaches exhibited reduced generalizability across different species and disease conditions when compared with deep learning-based models (Ahmed et al., 2021). More recent contributions to the field have a shift toward integrated and non-invasive fish health assessment frameworks. Hybrid model designs combining image-based disease detection with additional sensing modalities such as environmental monitoring measurements enabled disease interpretation within the surrounding environmental conditions (Zhang et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2023). Such frameworks support early warning and preventive management strategies and represent progress toward precision aquaculture applications. Hybrid ML–DL architectures integrating multiple algorithms have been proposed to combine the strengths of different modeling approaches. Studies incorporating Internet of Things (IoT)–based environmental monitoring in combination with image-based deep learning models reported improved disease prediction through the association of water quality parameters with observed visual symptoms (Timmis et al., 2017). Such hybrid systems suggest a movement toward more integrated approaches to aquaculture health management. Nevertheless, considerable variation in reported performance was observed, attributable to

differences in image quality, species specificity, data collection conditions, and validation procedures. In many cases, model performance was assessed under controlled experimental conditions, thereby limiting the applicability of reported accuracy measures to operational aquaculture settings. These observations indicate the need for standardized datasets and uniform evaluation frameworks to permit reliable comparison among studies.

Figure 1. Conceptual workflow illustrating AI-driven fish disease detection in aquaculture systems. Source: Authors' conceptual synthesis based on reviewed literature (Noga, 2010; Ahmed et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2024; Isaac et al., 2024).

Table 1. Summary of peer-reviewed studies included in the systematic review on AI-driven fish disease detection published between 2019 and 2025. Data are compiled and synthesized by the author following PRISMA-guided literature screening.

Author (Year)	Fish Species / System	Disease / Health Focus	Data Type	AI Technique Used	Key Findings
Ahmed et al. (2021)	Multiple cultured species	Surface lesions	Image	Machine learning classifiers	Feasibility of image-based disease detection
Azhar et al. (2024)	Freshwater fish	White spot disease	Image	Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)	Early disease screening using deep learning
Wang et al. (2023)	Intensive aquaculture systems	Multiple visible diseases	Underwater images	YOLOv5-based CNN	Robust detection in underwater conditions

Zhang et al. (2024)	Farmed fish	General health and stress indicators	Image + impedance sensing	Deep learning multi-index system	Non-invasive fish health assessment
Isaac et al. (2024)	Multiple fish species	Visible disease symptoms	Image	Transfer learning with XAI	Improved interpretability and classification

Figure 2. Heatmap illustrating the relative representation of artificial intelligence techniques across the studies included in this review. Darker shading indicates greater reported use of a given technique, while lighter shading indicates limited or no application. Source: Authors' qualitative synthesis based on PRISMA-guided analysis of studies published predominantly between 2021 and 2024.

Figure 3. Comparison of reported performance trends across different artificial intelligence techniques applied in fish disease detection studies. Source: Authors' synthesis based on reported outcomes in the reviewed literature (Ahmed et al., 2021; Azhar et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2024).

Discussion

Deep learning models like convolutional neural networks were most commonly applied for identifying externally visible disease symptoms. This reflects the suitability of image-based procedures for detecting visible changes such as

lesions, discoloration, and abnormal morphological patterns, which are frequently associated with common fish diseases. The findings of this systematic review shows that artificial intelligence has become an increasingly crucial tool for fish disease detection in fish, particularly through image-

based analysis and non-invasive monitoring methods. The deep learning methods observed in this review is because of their ability to automatically extract complex visual features without the need for manual expertise. Studies applying CNN-based models demonstrated performance under controlled experimental conditions, supporting their potential for early disease screening in aquaculture systems (Ahmed et al., 2021; Azhar et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2023). However, the effectiveness of these models depends on quality image data and standardized data collection procedures, which are not always easy to take underwater. Although deep learning approaches dominated recent research, traditional machine learning methods were also represented in the reviewed literature. These have advantages in terms of lower computational requirements and simpler implementation but were generally limited because of manually handling, reduced adaptability across species and disease types. A notable methodological development highlighted by this review is the growing integrated and non-invasive fish health assessment systems. Hybrid frameworks combining image-based disease detection with environmental and sensor obtained data were reported to provide a broader basis for the interpretation of disease risk. By relating visible disease signs to surrounding environmental conditions, including water quality stressors, such approaches support more anticipatory and preventive forms of health management in aquaculture systems (Zhang et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2023). This integration is consistent with the aims of precision aquaculture and reflects a gradual shift from reactive disease diagnosis to continuous health monitoring.

Many investigations were conducted under controlled experimental conditions, with limited validation across different farming systems, species, and environmental settings. Variations in image quality, sensor availability, and data acquisition protocols hinder direct comparison of reported outcomes and restrict the applicability of model performance to operational aquaculture environments. These observations indicate the need for standardized datasets and uniform evaluation frameworks to allow reliable comparison among studies. Furthermore, although deep learning models demonstrate strong predictive capability, their limited interpretability may constrain transparency and reduce user confidence when automated outputs are used to inform management decisions. Recent work has emphasized the importance of explainable artificial intelligence techniques to improve model transparency and facilitate practical adoption by farmers and aquaculture managers (Isaac et al., 2024; Islam et al., 2024). Incorporating interpretability into AI-driven diagnostic tools is therefore significant for bridging the gap between research development and under water implementation.

The result of this study shows that AI using fish disease detection methods has progressed markedly in recent years, though image based and hybrid monitoring methods. However, translating these technological advances into scalable and cost-effective solutions will require further research on field validation, model robustness, interpretability, and practical deployment. Addressing these problems will be critical for ensuring that AI-based disease detection systems contribute meaningfully to sustainable aquaculture health management.

Table 2. Comparative overview of artificial intelligence techniques used in fish disease detection. Classification and evaluation generated by the author.

AI Technique	Input Data	Key Strengths	Main Limitations	Representative References
Traditional Machine Learning	Fish images	Low computational cost; simple models	Manual feature extraction; limited scalability	Ahmed et al. (2021)

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)	Fish images	Automatic feature extraction; high accuracy	Requires large labeled datasets	Ahmed et al. (2021); Azhar et al. (2024); Wang et al. (2023)
Transfer Learning	Fish images	Effective with small datasets; faster training	Potential bias from pre-trained models	Azhar et al. (2024); Isaac et al. (2024)
Hybrid Image-Sensor Systems	Images + sensor data	Context-aware disease assessment	Increased system complexity	Zhang et al. (2024); Wang et al. (2023)
Explainable AI Models	Fish images	Improved transparency and trust	Limited real-world deployment	Isaac et al. (2024)

Conclusion:

This systematic review examined recent research published between 2019 and 2025 on artificial intelligence based methods for fish disease detection, with particular emphasis on imagebased techniques and integrated monitoring approaches. The reviewed literature path that deep learning and related computational methods have increasingly been applied for the identification of externally visible disease signs in fish. Such approaches provide an alternative to conventional diagnostic methods by allowing more rapid and non-invasive assessment, primarily under controlled experimental conditions. These observations suggest a gradual movement toward the combined use of visual analysis and supplementary information sources, including environmental data. Such integration allows disease predictions to be interpreted in relation to surrounding conditions and supports early warning. While these developments have potential, their application remains limited to experimental. It states existing studies rely on limited datasets, species-specific models, and controlled environments. Differences in data collection methods and evaluation criteria further complicate comparison between studies. Also, the limited interpretability of many AI models remains a practical concern, as transparent decision is essential for adoption by farmers. Future research should therefore focus less on performance improvements and more on issues related to interpretation and real-world applicability. Focus should made on 1 standardized datasets, field validation, and system design will be necessary to translate current research into reliable tools for fish disease detection. Keeping this in priorities will help ensure that AI-based

disease detection systems contribute meaningfully to sustainable health management of fish.

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